

TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve

Photopoint metadata v2.1

Background

Photographs have been taken approximately annually from 1926 until 2024 at a series of set positions (photopoints) by staff and students of the University of Adelaide. The information offered through the TERN Data Discovery Portal ([TDDP](#)) consists of the images themselves, delivered through [TERN Ecolimages](#), and observations derived from the photographs. The duration of the record available digitally extends from 1907 (observations) to 2008 (photographs), depending on the type of record. Tables 1, 2 and 3 provide details of the date ranges.

There are three types of photopoints, those from stand-alone positions (n=37), the corners of quadrats (n=26), and those from points along transects (n=10) (Figure 1). Each photopoint has a unique number and its location recorded. Each quadrat has two photopoints, usually but not always located at or near the northeast and northwest corners, the direction of each photograph being inward to the quadrat (see Hall et al., 1964). Photographs were taken in black and white or colour (largely dependent on year) and for the first many decades stored as prints with negatives. During 2007-2008 the photo archive was digitised by Dr Dean Graetz using the photonegative collection. It is due to his efforts that we have nearly 6,000 digital copies of the photographs archived and made available on [TERN Ecolimages](#). For access to the original hardcopy images and other records, contact the University Archives and/or the School of Biological Sciences at the University of Adelaide.

The consistency of the photographic record between 1926 and 2008 (the time frame available from this source) is variable: some photopoints have an almost continuous observational record (e.g. PP1), while others are of shorter duration (e.g. the 20 years from 1968-1988). Observations including measurements taken from the photographs do not carry forward beyond 1988, except for PP15 and PP1 whose measurements extend respectively to 1989 and 1994.

Figure 1: Sketch map of the type and distribution of measurements at the TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve. Not all photopoint positions are shown, and the scale is approximate. Bindy-I is the field laboratory. The map is derived from Osborn *et al.*, 1935, Hall *et al.*, 1964, Crisp, unpublished map, 1972, lists of georeferences for many of the locations, and Google maps.

Reserve coordinates: NE corner: -32.10834° 139.35187°, SE corner: -32.12459° 139.35141°, SW corner: -32.12401° 139.32794°, NW corner: -32.10767° 139.32858°.

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Methods

Since October, 1977 most stand-alone photopoints were defined by a steel stake marking the location of the camera and another, painted in 20cm strips, 15m from the camera defining the centre of the field of view. For many years photos were taken with a SLR camera (type noted in original records) using a 50mm lens. A black and white photo was initially taken, and by the 1970's a colour photo was taken as well, until colour photographs were only taken. The photographs were printed and mounted on record cards with details of the camera and film used, the negative number and photographer. Each photograph was annotated according to what could be seen on the photograph, individual species identified, numbers given to each plant (not always reliable from event to event) and occasionally plants measured. It is the data from these and the photographs associated to them that are found in the [TDDP](#) and [TERN Ecolimages](#) respectively.

The availability of images and observations from them is shown in the following tables, Table 1 for stand-alone photopoints, Table 2 for quadrat photos and Table 3 for transect and fire quadrat photos.

Table 1: Earliest and latest dates in the TERN collection for stand-alone photopoints. Collections between these dates can be intermittent. Photographs are available in [TERN Ecolimages](#), observational data and guide to the ID of the photos available in the [TDDP](#).

photopoint ID	photographs	observations	photopoint ID	photographs	observations
PP1	1930-1994	1928-1994	PP15	1935-2008	1929-1989
PP2	1931-2007	1928-1987	PP20	1946-2008	1943-1988
PP3	1931-2008	1954-1985	PP24	1948-2008	1947-1988
PP4L	1928-2008	1928-1985	PP25	1950-2008	1950-1988
PP4R	1928-2008	1928-1986	PP26	1946-2008	1968-1988
PP4Panorama	1935-2008	none	PP27	1946-2008	1944-1988
PP5	1925-2008	1925-1988	PP28	1946-2008	1944-1988
PP6	1931-2008	1938-1988	PP28A	1946-2008	1947-1988
PP7	1930-2008	1923-1988	PP29	1946-2008	1944-1988
PP8	1930-2008	1928-1988	PP30	1946-2008	1944-1988
PP9	1930-2008	1927-1988	PP31	1968-2008	1968-1988
PP10in	1931-2008	1929-1988	PP32	1968-2008	1968-1988
PP10out	1931-2008	1929-1988	PP33	1968-2008	1968-1988
PP11	1931-2008	1931-1988	PP34	1968-2008	1968-1988
PP11super	1937-2008	1932-1988	PP35	1968-2008	1968-1988
PP12	1935-2008	1907-1988	PP36	1968-2008	1968-1988
PP13	1930-2008	1931-1988			

Table 2: Earliest and latest dates in the TERN collection for photographs taken at quadrats. Collections between these dates can be very intermittent. Photographs are available in [TERN Ecolimages](#), observational data and guide to the ID of the photos available in the [TDDP](#).

quadrat photopoint ID	photographs	observations	quadrat photopoint ID	photographs	observations
ppQ100NW	1928-2008	1935-1988	ppQ40NE	1970-2008	1926-1988
ppQ100SE	1928-2008	1926-1988	ppQ40NW	1972-2008	1926-1988
ppQ10ANE	1928-2008	1926-1988	ppQ400NE	1928-2008	1926-1988
ppQ10ANW	1928-2008	1929-1988	ppQ400NW	1928-2008	1926-1988
ppQ1NE	1928-1931	none	ppQ40ANE	1928-2008	1926-1988
ppQ1NW	1928-1931	none	ppQ40ANW	1928-2008	1926-1988
ppQ200N	1928-2008	1926-1988	ppQ40BNE	1928-2008	1928-1988
ppQ200S	1928-2008	1926-1988	ppQ40BNW	1928-2008	1927-1988
ppQ30E	1928-2008	1930-1988	ppQ6-80NW	1928-2008	1927-1988
ppQ30W	1928-2008	1926-1988	ppQ6-80SE	1928-2008	1927-1988
ppQ300N-S	1928-2008	1926-1988	ppQ60NE	1928-2008	1927-1988
ppQ300N-SE	1928-2008	1926-1988	ppQ60NW	1928-2008	1927-1988

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Table 3: Earliest and latest dates in the TERN collection for photographs taken at transects and fire quadrats. Collections between these dates can be very intermittent. Photographs are available in [TERN Ecoimages](#), observational data and guide to the ID of the photos available in the [TDDP](#).

photopoint ID	photographs	observations	photopoint ID	photographs	observations
TR1PP1	1930-2008	1930-1988	TR4PPdelta	1936-2008	1931-1988
TR1PP2	1930-2008	1939-1988	TR4PPepsilon	1936-2008	1929-1988
TR1PP3	1930-2008	1930-1988	TR4PPgamma	1936-2008	1929-1988
TR1PP5	1936-2008	1931-1988	FRA1	1938-2008	1937-1988
TR2PP4	1930-2008	1930-1988	FR4A	1938-2008	1944-1988
TR3PPalpha	1937-2008	1929-1988	FR6	1935-2008	1938-1988
TR3PPbeta	1937-2008	1929-1988			

When more than one image is available per photopoint per date of observation, a maximum of four images is listed in the observation file. Each image is named by photopoint ID, the date of the image (photopointID_yyyymmdd) and a unique sequence number. These match directly across both sources, TERN Ecoimages and the [TDDP](#) observation file. If black and white and colour images are both available for the same date and location, at least one of each is included in the four images available.

Dr Graetz created videos showing the changes at each photopoint. These uncatalogued videos have been posted on YouTube and can be seen at: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sJfw1QvPKt4>.

Physical information about the measurement data set

This data set is composed of an excel (csv) file of 1.9 MB, a data dictionary and attribute metadata.

Attribute information about the data set

Records are as follows:

Photopoint_ID, Latitude (Decimal Degrees), Longitude (Decimal Degrees), Measurement date (YYYY-MM-DD), name of available images (1-4), PlantID, Scientific Name (of the individual organism), Crown Diameter North South (cm), Crown Diameter East West (cm), Height (cm), Life Stage, Individual Occurrence Comment and Feature comments.

Each image name is as follows: photopointID_yyyymmdd_seqn

References

Hall, E.A.A., Specht, R.L. and Eardley, C.M. (1964) Regeneration of the vegetation on Koonamore Vegetation Reserve, 1926 - 1962. *Aust. J. Bot.* 12: 205-264.

Osborn, T.G.B., Wood, J.G. and Paltridge, T.B. (1935) On the climate and vegetation of the Koonamore Vegetation Reserve to 1931. *Proc. Linn. Soc. NSW.* 60: 392-427.

Change log for the photopoint data and image collection

version, year	editor	features
V1, 2008-2014	Russell Sinclair	digitised field data sheets and computer records to be delivered to the AEKOS TERN portal added required V1 metadata in the AEKOS-TERN portal
V2, 2025-05-27	Alison Specht	cleaned observation data file, correcting scientific names gathered images, catalogued them, sorted them into those related to measurement types
	Miranda Fittock, Wilma Karsdorp and Javier Sanchez Gonzalez	re-named photos to be consistent throughout (photopointID_yyyymmdd). Arranged for them to be uploaded into TERN Ecoimages
	Fittock and Specht	entered photograph names into observation file and delivered the file to the TERN Data Discovery Portal.
	Specht	created this metadata file including catalogue of holdings
V2.1, 2026-02-04	Fittock, Specht and Arun Singh Ramesh	Updated dates to comply with ISO standards (YYYY-MM-DD). Clarified anomalies in the record and inserted NA in blank cells, cells with 'no comment' etc.